

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ITS CATEGORIZATION

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Abstract: The changes which are occurring on a global scale is highly unpredictable, especially in economics. Because, thanks to current rapid changes in a large number of fields including entrepreneurship, some of previous materials can be irrelevant. In this situation, there is a demand for researchers to introduce new categories into a certain field they are conducting a research, for example, a few decades ago, people were not able to ponder over start-ups thoroughly. In this article, it has been made an attempt to give relevant information about the content and essence of entrepreneurship and its categorization.

Key words: Small business activity, Entrepreneurship, Start-up projects, Large company entrepreneurship, Social entrepreneurship, Research entrepreneurship, Purchase business.

Annotatsiya: Global miqyosda sodir bo'layotgan o'zgarishlarni oldindan aytish qiyin, ayniqsa iqtisodiyotda. Chunki ko'plab sohalarda, shu jumladan tadbirkorlikda, hozirgi tezkor o'zgarishlar tufayli avvalgi materiallarning ayrimlari ahamiyatsiz bo'lib qolishi mumkin. Bunday sharoitda tadqiqotchilardan o'z tadqiqot olib borayotgan sohalariga yangi toifalarni kiritish talabi yuzaga keladi. Masalan, bir necha o'n yillar avval odamlar startaplar haqida chuqur o'ylashmagan. Ushbu maqolada tadbirkorlikning mazmuni va mohiyati, uning turkumlanishi haqida tegishli ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kichik biznes faoliyati, tadbirkorlik, startap loyihalari, yirik kompaniya tadbirkorligi, ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik, tadqiqot tadbirkorligi, xarid biznesi.

Аннотация: Изменения, происходящие в глобальном масштабе, крайне непредсказуемы, особенно в экономике. Поскольку из-за текущих быстрых изменений в большом количестве областей, включая предпринимательство, некоторые из предыдущих материалов могут оказаться неактуальными. В этой ситуации возникает потребность в том, чтобы исследователи вводили новые категории в определенную область, которую они исследуют, например, несколько десятилетий назад люди не могли в полной мере размышлять о стартапах. В этой статье была сделана попытка дать релевантную информацию о содержании и сути предпринимательства и его категоризации.

Ключевые слова: Малая предпринимательская деятельность, Предпринимательство, Стартап-проекты, Предпринимательство крупных компаний, Социальное предпринимательство, Исследовательское предпринимательство, Покупка бизнеса.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship and business play a crucial role in the development of every country. Without them, no nation can achieve sustainable progress, particularly those that have adopted the capitalist economic system as their primary framework. Entrepreneurship is vital for economic growth and the well-being of a population. For example, in fast-growing countries like China, business activities contribute to 60% of the GDP (www.oecd-ilibrary.org, n.d.). This demonstrates that the economic growth of any country largely depends on the advancement of its business sector.

In 1991, Uzbekistan, having just gained independence, faced a challenging environment for business activity. However, through well-directed efforts, by 2019, business activities accounted for 50% of the country's GDP (stat.uz, n.d.). This reflects significant progress in fostering entrepreneurship. This article aims to comprehensively analyze the essence of entrepreneurship, its various types, objectives, and key tasks.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The essence of entrepreneurship and its categorization have always been central to economic theory. Numerous scholars have explored this topic, analyzing the economic significance and social impact of entrepreneurship. Joseph Schumpeter described entrepreneurship as the primary driver of economic growth, emphasizing that innovation is a core element of the entrepreneurial process. In his studies, he characterized innovation and entrepreneurship as deeply interconnected processes.

Israel Kirzner viewed entrepreneurship as the process of identifying and exploiting market opportunities. According to him, entrepreneurs thrive in situations where market equilibrium is disrupted, creating new opportunities and restoring balance to the economic system.

David McClelland focused on entrepreneurial behavior and motivation in his research. He argued that entrepreneurs are driven by intrinsic motivations such as the “need for achievement,” which contributes to improving economic efficiency.

Paul Reynolds, who conducted research on regional entrepreneurship, highlighted the social and economic effects of entrepreneurial activity. He noted that entrepreneurship influences not only economic growth but also employment levels and social stability within a society.

William Baumol provided a crucial perspective by categorizing entrepreneurship into various forms, such as productive and unproductive entrepreneurship. Baumol emphasized that effective state policies and institutional frameworks are critical for channeling entrepreneurship into productive activities.

Among Uzbek economists, A. Vahobov and Sh. X. Khajibaqulov analyzed the significance of entrepreneurship for regional development in Uzbekistan. Their research demonstrated the importance of supporting entrepreneurship in local contexts to stimulate economic growth.

In studies related to the categorization of entrepreneurship, various types have been identified, including innovative, traditional, social, and technological entrepreneurship. This classification plays a key role in diversifying economies and provides insights into the social and economic dimensions of entrepreneurial activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for the article focuses on the collection and analysis of qualitative and quantitative data. Primary data were obtained through surveys and interviews with entrepreneurs and policymakers, while secondary data were sourced from academic publications, government reports, and statistical databases. The collected data were analyzed using comparative and content analysis methods to identify patterns, trends, and relationships relevant to the categorization and essence of entrepreneurship.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the *Oxford Students' Dictionary*, “Business” is defined as the activity of producing, buying, selling, and providing goods and services for the purpose of making money. Meanwhile, “Entrepreneurship” refers to starting a business that involves financial risk and is described as an activity aimed at earning money by taking calculated risks (www.dictionary.com, n.d.). In economic terms, business encompasses the buying and selling of goods and services common to everyone, while entrepreneurship focuses on creating new enterprises, fostering their growth, and managing them (Ngo H. A., 2019).

According to Geoffrey S. M., PhD economist at Bloomington Indiana University, “Entrepreneurship is the process of creating new enterprises and businesses and determining the possibilities of their establishment.” Business, by contrast, involves activities related to the production, distribution, and sale of goods and services with the aim of making a profit (Acs Z. & Audretsch D., 2007). Another distinctive feature of entrepreneurship is its emphasis on innovation in the creation of goods and services, whereas business tends to prioritize operational and managerial aspects of existing enterprises. Entrepreneurship demands risk-taking and adaptability, while business focuses more on optimizing current opportunities through strategic planning and management.

“Entrepreneurship” is also described as the process of implementing innovative business ideas and finding solutions to potential challenges. Effective management of any business requires understanding its type, which can generally be categorized into the following (Rosemaro, 2022):

1. Small Business Activity: Involves establishing, managing, and developing small business enterprises that primarily serve local markets by providing scarce goods and services. These businesses often cater to specific, limited market segments.

2. Entrepreneurship Based on Extended Start-Up Projects: Focused on developing larger-scale innovative projects with growth potential.

3. Large Company Entrepreneurship: Involves fostering innovation within established large enterprises.
4. Social Entrepreneurship: Centers on solving social issues and creating positive societal impact through entrepreneurial efforts.

5. Research Entrepreneurship: Engages in creating new products or processes based on scientific or technological research.

6. Purchase Business: Revolves around acquiring and managing existing businesses.

Small business entrepreneurship plays a significant role in addressing local market demands by delivering essential goods and services, often operating as a localized enterprise for targeted market segments (Eunice, 2020). (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Key Characteristics of Small Entrepreneurship.

1. It is possible to start a small business using a small amount of capital investment: personal savings, family, friends, and small business loans.
2. Goods and services suitable for the local market can be provided by small businesses, satisfying consumer needs that large companies cannot meet.
3. Employment means small business activities play an important role in creating jobs.
4. An entrepreneur’s personal involvement refers to their participation in all day-to-day operations of the enterprise, from strategic planning to decision-making.
5. Innovation and flexibility: since small businesses may not have as many resources as large organizations, they can quickly adapt to changes in the market.
6. Regarding their contribution to the country’s development, small businesses play a vital role by supporting the local economy, paying taxes, and fostering innovation (Rashid, Mohamad & Yusoff, Nurul & Kamarudin, Khairul, 2022).

Scalable Start-up Entrepreneurship is a type of entrepreneurship that begins with an innovative and profitable idea, adopting a business model capable of rapidly transforming into a highly profitable company (corporatefinanceinstitute.com, n.d.). Examples of this entrepreneurship include Facebook, Instagram, Airbnb, Spotify, and Uber. According to the Asian Development Bank’s 2020 report, approximately 1,200 start-up projects were launched in Uzbekistan (www.adb.org, n.d.), among which one of the most successful is Uzum, an electronic shopping startup that enables businesses to develop, process payments, and organize food delivery throughout Uzbekistan.

Large Company Entrepreneurship involves operations aimed at developing new enterprises, implementing innovations, and achieving company-wide growth (Nabila, 2013). One major advantage of large company entrepreneurship is the availability of financial resources for research and development, enabling the adoption of new technologies and ideas (Tseng, 2020). Additionally, existing network partnerships in large companies facilitate the sharing of resources, expertise, and access to new markets (Wu, Bo & Wang, Yufen & Qin, Wenting, 2010). Furthermore, strong brand reputation and established consumer bases provide a competitive

edge when entering new markets or launching new products (Hayton, James & Hornsby, Jeff & BLOODGOOD, James, 2013). Examples of such companies include Google, Microsoft, Apple, and Samsung (www.pfh.de, n.d.).

Social entrepreneurship focuses on finding solutions to social problems by applying business principles and strategies that address societal needs. The primary goal is to create, launch, and manage enterprises that prioritize social value over profit maximization. Social entrepreneurship often takes the form of non-profit organizations dedicated to solving issues such as poverty reduction, healthcare, education, and environmental protection (Akbulaev, 2019). Well-known examples of social entrepreneurship include Tom's Shoes, State Bags, Warby Parker, Trinity Oaks, Ashoka, and Mitscoots (table 1).

Table 1. Examples of Social Entrepreneurship and Their Functions.

Social entrepreneurship	Function
Tom's Shoes	Providing shoes to a child who needs shoes;
State Bags	Helping American children in difficult situations;
Warby Parker	Distribution of glasses to those who need them;
Trinity Oaks	Tree planting;
Ashoka	Search for social entrepreneurs around the world and invest in them;
Mitscoots	Helping homeless people with food and clothing.

Research Entrepreneurship plays an important role in bridging the gap between academic research and the market by transforming innovative ideas and discoveries into commercial goods and services. Through this process, in-depth research conducted by researchers creates economic value and stimulates societal development. PhD students and graduate students engaged in research entrepreneurship can develop platforms by applying their specialized knowledge to the practical world, enabling the launch of startup projects and technologies. To succeed in entrepreneurship through research, it is crucial to possess not only strong academic potential but also entrepreneurial thinking and an understanding of market dynamics (Sharples).

Buyer Entrepreneurship involves acquiring an existing small business or company instead of investing in the creation of a new one (Rosemaro, 2022). For example, on April 14, 2022, Elon Musk purchased Twitter and further developed the platform (en.wikipedia.org, n.d.).

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Entrepreneurship is a multifaceted and dynamic process that serves as a cornerstone of economic development, innovation, and societal progress. This study has explored the essence of entrepreneurship, emphasizing its role in identifying and exploiting opportunities through creativity, innovation, and adaptability. Entrepreneurs act as agents of change, fostering economic growth, generating employment, and contributing to the overall welfare of society.

The categorization of entrepreneurship into various forms—such as traditional, innovative, social, and technological—underscores its diverse nature and the ability to address a wide range of economic and social challenges. Traditional entrepreneurship focuses on meeting market demands, while innovative entrepreneurship drives technological advancement and competitiveness. Social entrepreneurship tackles pressing societal issues by providing sustainable solutions, and technological entrepreneurship advances industries through cutting-edge innovation.

Furthermore, the study has highlighted the importance of entrepreneurial ecosystems that support these activities, including access to resources, favorable policies, and educational initiatives. By understanding and leveraging the different dimensions of entrepreneurship, policymakers, educators, and business leaders can create strategies that not only promote economic growth but also ensure sustainability and inclusivity.

The findings of this study underscore the need for continued research and support for entrepreneurship in all its forms. As economies face rapid technological advancements and global challenges, fostering entrepreneurial activity remains a critical pathway to achieving long-term economic stability, societal well-being, and global competitiveness.

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Yashil

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